

A Penalty-Free Pipeline for Direct Quantum-Annealer Portfolio Optimization

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Abstract

Direct quantum-annealer portfolio optimization is commonly formulated as a penalty-encoded QUBO and submitted to D-Wave hardware. We show that this standard formulation fails on current devices and identify the structural reason: the cardinality penalty $A(\mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{x} - K)^2$ contributes a dense rank-one matrix $A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$ that makes the logical graph complete regardless of Σ . On Pegasus and Zephyr, chains break at 83% at $N = 24$ and 92% at $N = 49$, producing no feasible samples.

Attempting to fix this through topology-aware sparsification reveals a second problem: any sparsifier that removes off-diagonal entries also dilutes the cardinality constraint. Raw samples remain infeasible even when chains no longer break. An ablation shows that for structurally favorable cases (betting with settlement-graph priors) the classical feasibility projector alone explains the result, not the QPU.

We propose dropping the penalty entirely: build the objective-only QUBO $Q_{\text{obj}} = -\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda\Sigma$, sample on hardware, and enforce cardinality classically. On D-Wave Advantage and Advantage2 for equities up to $N = 49$ and betting up to $N = 48$, mean chain-break fractions (per sample, averaged over reads) drop from 71–92% to at most 0.04%. The QPU returns lower-energy feasible portfolios than the greedy heuristic on betting at $N \in \{39, 48\}$ (an energy comparison, not a proof of optimality), and equity post-processed regret is at most 0.03% at all tested scales. These results establish that the penalty encoding, not the sparse hardware topology, is the binding constraint for direct QPU portfolio optimization at currently accessible scales.

Keywords: quantum annealing; portfolio optimization; QUBO sparsification; minor embedding; Pegasus and Zephyr; sports betting

1 Introduction

Portfolio optimization (Markowitz 1952) is one of the most frequently discussed applications for quantum annealing (Orús et al. 2019; Herman et al. 2023; Venturelli and Kondratyev 2019; Mugel et al. 2022; Grant et al. 2021). The idea is straightforward: formulate asset selection as a quadratic unconstrained binary optimization (QUBO) problem and submit it to a quantum processing unit (QPU). In practice, however, this approach faces a structural obstacle that is often understated in the literature. The logical interaction graph of a dense portfolio QUBO must be embedded onto the sparse hardware topology of the QPU through minor embedding (Choi 2008, 2011), a process that introduces auxiliary chain qubits and rapidly degrades solution quality as the problem grows (D-Wave Systems 2025b; Grant and Humble 2022).

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In the present work, we ask a question that we believe is prior to any discussion of quantum advantage: *why does direct portfolio optimization fail on current quantum annealers, and can the failure be fixed at currently accessible scales?* Our contribution is threefold: we diagnose the structural reason for the failure, we show that the most natural fix (topology-aware sparsification) does not work on its own, and we demonstrate that a simpler modification (dropping the penalty encoding entirely) produces a pipeline whose chain-break rates are essentially zero and whose post-processed solutions are competitive with classical references across the full experimental range we tested.

The diagnosis

The standard binary cardinality-constrained portfolio QUBO (Lucas 2014; Glover et al. 2019) takes the form $Q = -\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda\Sigma + A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top - 2AKI$, where $A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$ is a rank-one dense matrix contributed by the exact- K penalty $A(\mathbf{1}^\top\mathbf{x} - K)^2$. This term adds the value A to every off-diagonal entry of Q , making the logical interaction graph complete regardless of the structure of Σ . This is the key observation of the paper: *the QUBO is dense because of the encoding, not because of the underlying financial structure*. For a betting slate with block-diagonal payoff covariance, the penalty inflates an instance from $3M$ edges (one 3-clique per match) to $\binom{3M}{2}$ edges (complete graph). For equities, where the empirical covariance matrix is already dense, the penalty compounds the problem.

On live D-Wave Advantage and Advantage2 hardware, the consequences are severe. Dense portfolio QUBOs at $N = 24$ ($K = 8$) yield mean chain lengths of 3.5–3.6 and chain-break fractions near 83%. At $N = 49$ (the full FF49 universe, $K = 12$), mean chain lengths grow to 6.59 on Pegasus and 5.23 on Zephyr, and chain breaks to 88–92%. The feasible sample rate is 0% at every scale: not one of several thousand reads returns a binary vector with exactly K ones.

The failed fix: sparsify and project

A natural response is topology-aware sparsification: replace Q with a sparse approximation \tilde{Q} , let it embed with short chains, and handle the resulting infeasibility with classical post-processing. We study four sparsification families (threshold, top- k , domain-prior, and domain-prior with residual edges) and show that they do reduce chain breaks to essentially zero. However, any sparsifier that removes off-diagonal entries also removes penalty weight proportionally, diluting the cardinality constraint. Raw samples become infeasible even when chains no longer break. An ablation shows that on the betting settlement-graph case, the zero-regret result is explained entirely by the projector’s backward-elimination behavior on a block-diagonal-plus-penalty QUBO, not by the QPU itself. Sparsification plus projection is a working pipeline, but the QPU contribution is unclear and the result is dominated by classical post-processing.

The simpler fix: drop the penalty

The diagnosis suggests a more direct approach. If the penalty is the sole source of density for structurally sparse problems (betting) and a major source for dense ones (equities), one can simply remove it: build the objective-only QUBO $Q_{\text{obj}} = -\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda\Sigma$, sample on the QPU, and enforce $\sum_i x_i = K$ through classical post-processing. We validate this penalty-free pipeline on live hardware for equities ($N \in \{24, 32, 40, 49\}$) and betting ($N \in \{30, 39, 48\}$). Live chain-break fractions drop from 71–92% (penalized, across both case studies) to at most 0.04% across all scales. For betting, post-processed QPU solutions at $N = 39$ and $N = 48$ are better than the greedy classical reference (the QPU finds lower-energy feasible portfolios than the backward-elimination heuristic). For equities, post-processed regret is at most 0.03% relative to greedy construction across all tested scales, including the full $N = 49$ universe.

Contributions

1. We identify the structural source of failure in direct-QPU portfolio optimization as the dense rank-one penalty term $A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$, not the sparse hardware topology itself.
2. We demonstrate empirically that topology-aware sparsification of penalty-encoded QUBOs creates a second failure mode, which we call *constraint dilution*, and that an ablation reveals the sparsify-and-project pipeline is dominated by the classical projector in structurally favorable cases.
3. We propose and validate a penalty-free pipeline (Q_{obj} on hardware plus classical feasibility projection) that yields essentially zero chain breaks and competitive post-processed regret across the full experimental range ($N \leq 49$ for equities, $N \leq 48$ for betting) on both Pegasus and Zephyr.
4. We report all results with honest baselines: greedy construction, all-ones projection, and random projection. We do not claim quantum advantage. We claim that the penalty encoding, not the hardware, is the binding constraint for direct-QPU portfolio optimization at currently accessible scales.

We validate our findings on two case studies using public data: Kenneth French 49 industry daily portfolios (French 2026) and pre-match football 1X2 odds from football-data.co.uk (Football-Data.co.uk 2025). The betting case provides a structurally favorable contrast (naturally block-diagonal covariance) that isolates the penalty encoding as the sole source of density.

This article is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews relevant literature. Section 3 introduces the portfolio QUBO formulation and derives the penalty-induced density explicitly. Section 4 presents the sparsification methods and the constraint-dilution analysis. Section 5 describes the experimental protocol. Section 6 presents the results, organized as (i) the failure of dense penalty-encoded QUBOs, (ii) the sparsify-and-project pipeline with its ablation, and (iii) the penalty-free pipeline. We discuss the implications in Section 7 and conclude in Section 8.

Relationship to a companion paper. A companion paper by the same author (Lozano 2026) addresses an adjacent but distinct practitioner question. The present paper asks how to make *direct-QPU* portfolio optimization work, and proposes a custom penalty-free pipeline (objective-only QUBO sampled on hardware, with classical feasibility projection). The companion paper instead benchmarks D-Wave’s existing *hybrid* service interfaces (LeapHybridBQM versus LeapHybridCQM) for the same problem class, with a Gurobi MIQP optimality anchor and a multi-axis (size, density, budget) experimental grid. The two papers share a root diagnosis (the cardinality penalty contributes a dense rank-one matrix that makes the logical graph complete regardless of Σ), but they apply that diagnosis in two different layers of the D-Wave stack and reach two different practical recommendations. The present paper does not address the hybrid CQM/BQM choice; the companion paper does not address the direct-QPU pipeline architecture. Each paper can be read independently.

2 Related Work

Several works have explored quantum annealing for portfolio optimization. Venturelli and Kondratyev (2019) demonstrated reverse quantum annealing on small portfolio instances, showing that annealing schedules can be tuned to improve solution quality. Mugel et al. (2022) applied D-Wave processors to dynamic portfolio optimization with up to 52 assets, though their approach relies on hybrid solvers rather than direct QPU access. Sakuler et al. (2025) reported results on real-world portfolio data using quantum annealing. Rosenberg et al. (2016) was among the

first to apply D-Wave hardware to a financial optimization problem, formulating optimal trading trajectories as QUBOs.

Several recent portfolio-optimization studies have also benchmarked quantum and quantum-inspired workflows against classical references. Lang et al. (2022) compare simulated, digital, and quantum annealing after a classical preprocessing step; Buonaiuto et al. (2023) study best-practice choices for portfolio optimization on real quantum devices; Acharya et al. (2025) propose a decomposition pipeline for large constrained portfolio and rebalancing problems; and Stopfer and Wagner (2025) provide a broad benchmark in which classical MIP and tailored heuristics outperform quantum annealing and QAOA on the tested instances. These negative and mixed results are consistent with the cautionary stance of the present paper.

What these works have in common is that they either use hybrid solvers (which offload much of the computation to classical hardware) or they focus on the problem formulation without a detailed analysis of the embedding cost that dense interaction graphs impose on direct QPU access. Our work is complementary in the sense that we focus specifically on this structural question: how does the topology of the logical interaction graph determine whether direct-QPU access is viable at all? This is a question that exists independently of whether a hybrid solver can eventually solve the problem.

On the QUBO formulation side, the standard approach for mapping constrained optimization problems to Ising form is well established (Lucas 2014; Glover et al. 2019). The role of penalty weights in constraint enforcement has been studied by Verma and Lewis (2022), who showed that penalty magnitudes must be carefully calibrated: too small and the constraint is not enforced, too large and the penalty overwhelms the objective structure. Our work identifies a related but distinct problem: even with correctly calibrated penalties, the dense off-diagonal structure they produce conflicts with sparse hardware topologies, and sparsification of the QUBO matrix inadvertently removes penalty weight along with objective interactions. Concurrent work by Yasir and van Loock (2025) addresses a related question on the gate-based side: their IF-QAOA replaces quadratic penalty terms for inequality constraints with an oracle-based indicator function and reports higher solution quality and faster time-to-solution in the majority of their knapsack benchmarks. The two approaches are complementary (they target inequality constraints on QAOA circuits, while we target the equality cardinality constraint on direct quantum annealing), but both reflect a broader trend toward removing rather than tuning penalty terms in constrained quantum optimization.

The embedding problem itself was formalized by Choi (2008, 2011), who established the theoretical framework for minor embedding and parameter setting on quantum annealing hardware. Grant and Humble (2022) provided systematic benchmarks of chain-break behavior, and Pelofske (2025) compared embedding quality across three generations of D-Wave processors.

On the betting side, the connection between sports betting and portfolio optimization has been formalized by Uhrin et al. (2021), who review Kelly criterion (Kelly 1956) and Markowitz-based strategies with continuous stake sizing. For our purposes, the important insight from their work is the odds matrix representation and the portfolio framing of simultaneous bets. Wunderlich and Memmert (2020) showed that positive betting returns can be generated even in the absence of a superior forecasting model: the so-called profitability paradox. This result motivates our decision to evaluate betting outcomes with proper scoring rules (Brier score, log loss) alongside realized ROI, rather than treating profitability as a standalone measure of quality.

For the statistical evaluation of equity portfolio performance, we follow the published Sharpe-ratio inference literature of Lo (2002), Bailey and López de Prado (2012), and Bailey and López de Prado (2014). These works provide the corrected inference tools we use throughout our out-of-sample analysis.

3 Problem Formulation

3.1 From Portfolio Selection to QUBO

It is important to distinguish between the financial problem and its QUBO encoding, because the two have different structures and the encoding choice is central to the difficulties we identify.

The financial problem is cardinality-constrained portfolio selection: given a universe of n assets, select exactly K of them to hold, maximizing expected return minus risk. In the continuous Markowitz formulation (Markowitz 1952), this would involve continuous weights $w_i \in [0, 1]$ and a convex quadratic program. The cardinality-constrained binary version (select K assets with equal weight) is NP-hard in general but practically solvable for moderate n by classical methods. For practitioners, the exact- K constraint is not a cosmetic modeling choice: it represents operational limits on portfolio breadth, monitoring capacity, liquidity, and mandate design. A workflow that cannot reliably return exactly K selected positions is not directly usable in a portfolio-management system, regardless of how good its unconstrained QUBO energy appears.

To submit this problem to a quantum annealer, we must encode it as an unconstrained binary optimization (QUBO). The standard approach (Lucas 2014; Glover et al. 2019) replaces the hard cardinality constraint $\sum_i x_i = K$ with a quadratic penalty:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in \{0,1\}^n} -\boldsymbol{\mu}^\top \mathbf{x} + \lambda \mathbf{x}^\top \Sigma \mathbf{x} + A (\mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{x} - K)^2, \quad (1)$$

where $x_i = 1$ indicates that asset i is selected, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the expected return vector, Σ is the covariance matrix, $\lambda > 0$ is the risk-aversion parameter, and $A > 0$ is the penalty weight. When A is large enough, the penalty makes infeasible solutions ($\sum x_i \neq K$) energetically unfavorable, so the QUBO optimum coincides with the constrained optimum (Verma and Lewis 2022).

Expanding the penalty and collecting terms, the problem takes the standard QUBO form $f_Q(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}^\top Q \mathbf{x} + c$, where

$$Q = -\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda \Sigma + A \mathbf{1} \mathbf{1}^\top - 2AK I \quad (2)$$

and $c = AK^2$ is a constant offset. The key observation, and the source of the difficulties we report in this paper, is that the penalty term $A \mathbf{1} \mathbf{1}^\top$ contributes A to *every* off-diagonal entry of Q , making the interaction graph complete regardless of the structure of Σ . This means that even if the financial interactions are sparse (as they are in the betting case), the QUBO is guaranteed to be dense because of the encoding. For equities, the covariance matrix Σ is itself empirically dense (all industries correlate), so the QUBO would be dense even without the penalty. For betting, Σ is block-diagonal and the penalty is the sole source of density.

We emphasize that this is a property of the penalty encoding, not of portfolio optimization itself. The financial problem has sparse or structured interactions; the QUBO surrogate does not. This distinction is central to interpreting our results. Figure 1 illustrates the mechanism: the penalty term transforms any sparse interaction graph into a complete graph, which then requires long embedding chains on bounded-degree hardware topologies.

3.2 Equity Formulation

For the equity case study, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the rolling mean daily return estimated over a 252-trading-day window, and Σ is the sample covariance matrix over the same window. We rebalance monthly. From the Kenneth French 49 industry daily portfolios, we construct subsets of size $N \in \{12, 16, 20, 24\}$ by ranking all 49 industries by absolute mean return and selecting the top N . This is a long-only selection model: $x_i = 1$ means the industry is held, $x_i = 0$ means it is not. We rank by absolute signal to create heterogeneous test subsets with differentiated return profiles; this is a benchmark-instance construction rule, not an investable long-only screening strategy. At $N = 49$, the full universe is used without subsetting.

Figure 1: Penalty-dilution mechanism. Left: the original covariance graph may be sparse (few edges). Center: adding the cardinality penalty $A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$ makes the QUBO fully connected regardless of the original structure. Right: embedding the complete graph on bounded-degree hardware requires long chains that are prone to breaking during annealing.

3.3 Betting Formulation

For simultaneous pre-match bets with decimal odds d_i and win probabilities p_i (Uhrin et al. 2021), we construct the expected return and covariance as follows. The odds d_i are the best available across all bookmakers in the dataset for each outcome. The probabilities p_i are obtained by de-vigging each bookmaker’s implied probabilities using the proportional (multiplicative normalization) method (dividing each inverse-odds value by the bookmaker’s total overround) and then averaging across bookmakers to form a consensus probability. This gives:

$$\mu_i = d_i p_i - 1, \quad \Sigma_{ij} = \begin{cases} d_i^2 p_i (1 - p_i) & \text{if } i = j, \\ -d_i p_i d_j p_j & \text{if } i \neq j \text{ and same match,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

This gives Σ a natural block-diagonal structure: within each match, the three mutually exclusive 1X2 outcomes form a clique, while cross-match covariance is zero under the standard independence assumption. This structure provides a natural domain-prior graph for sparsification. Figure 2 illustrates the contrast: the settlement graph has only $3M$ edges (one triangle per match), while the penalty-encoded QUBO has $\binom{3M}{2}$ edges.

4 Topology-Aware Sparsification

4.1 Perturbation Analysis

Let $E = Q - \tilde{Q}$ be the perturbation matrix. For any binary vector \mathbf{x} with $\|\mathbf{x}\|_0 \leq K$:

$$|\mathbf{x}^\top E \mathbf{x}| \leq K \|E\|_2, \quad |\mathbf{x}^\top E \mathbf{x}| \leq K^2 \|E\|_{\max}. \quad (4)$$

If \mathbf{x}^* is the dense optimum and $\gamma = \min_{\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{x}^*} f_Q(\mathbf{x}) - f_Q(\mathbf{x}^*)$ is the optimality gap, then $\sup_{\mathbf{x}} |\mathbf{x}^\top E \mathbf{x}| < \gamma/2$ is sufficient for optimizer preservation.

Remark 1. In practice, the penalty term A dominates the off-diagonal entries of Q , making these bounds vacuous. For the $N = 24$, $K = 8$ frontier instance with threshold sparsification at the 75th percentile, the spectral bound gives 590, the max-entry bound gives 256, and the exact optimality gap is 1.7×10^{-4} , a ratio exceeding 10^6 . The bounds are therefore not useful for predicting optimizer preservation in this setting. We include them for completeness and rely on empirical regret measurements throughout.

Figure 2: Settlement graph versus penalty-encoded QUBO for a 3-match betting slate ($N = 9$). Left: the settlement graph has 9 edges (three disconnected 3-cliques). Right: the penalty-encoded QUBO has 36 edges (complete graph K_9) because the cardinality penalty $A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$ connects every pair of nodes.

4.2 Sparsification Methods

We study four methods, described algorithmically:

Threshold. Given threshold $\tau > 0$, set $\tilde{Q}_{ij} = Q_{ij}$ if $|Q_{ij}| \geq \tau$, and $\tilde{Q}_{ij} = 0$ otherwise, for $i \neq j$. Diagonal entries are always preserved.

Top- k . For each node i , retain the k off-diagonal entries with largest $|Q_{ij}|$. Symmetrize: if either (i, j) or (j, i) is retained, both are kept.

Domain-prior mask. Given a boolean mask M encoding a domain-specific interaction template, set $\tilde{Q}_{ij} = Q_{ij}$ if $M_{ij} = 1$, and $\tilde{Q}_{ij} = 0$ otherwise.

Domain-prior with residuals. Start from the domain-prior mask and add the top- r residual edges ranked by an importance matrix (e.g., absolute correlation).

Threshold and top- k are included as generic graph-compression baselines, not as financially interpretable priors. The finance-facing sparsifiers are the domain-prior methods. In equities, the k -nearest-neighbor correlation graph is a heuristic sparse proxy for concentrated co-risk; it is structurally informed, but not a causal model. In betting, the settlement graph is exact under our stated assumptions: same-match 1X2 outcomes are mutually exclusive, while cross-match outcomes are independent. We therefore interpret threshold/top- k primarily as topology baselines and the domain-prior rows as the economically structured comparison.

4.3 The Penalty–Sparsification Tension

A key structural finding of this work is the tension between QUBO penalty encoding and sparsification. The exact- K penalty in Equation (2) adds A to every off-diagonal entry. When any sparsification method zeroes out off-diagonal entries, it removes penalty weight proportional to the number of eliminated edges:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \text{removed}} A = A \cdot |\text{removed edges}|. \quad (5)$$

This weakens the cardinality constraint. In our experiments, this effect is severe: sparsified QUBOs produce raw QPU samples with $\sum_i x_i \gg K$, typically near all-ones vectors, because the penalty for selecting too many assets has been partially erased.

This tension is not specific to any particular sparsification method or problem domain. It arises whenever a penalty-encoded constraint produces dense off-diagonal contributions that dominate the objective structure. We observe identical behavior in both equity covariance portfolios and betting settlement portfolios.

5 Experimental Protocol

5.1 Instance Construction

Equities. We load the Kenneth French 49 industry daily portfolios and construct rolling instances with 252-day estimation windows and monthly rebalancing. We create subsets at $N \in \{12, 16, 20, 24\}$ with cardinalities $K \in \{4, 6, 8\}$ and risk aversion $\lambda \in \{0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$, and penalty weight $A = 4.0$ throughout. For the scaling experiments, we additionally test $N \in \{32, 40, 49\}$ with $K = 12$ and $\lambda = 1.0$; the $N = 49$ instance uses the full FF49 universe without subsetting. The domain-prior graph is built from k -nearest-neighbor correlations on the estimation-window covariance.

Betting. We load five European football leagues (EPL, La Liga, Serie A, Bundesliga, Ligue 1) for seasons 2020/21 through 2024/25, totaling 8,981 matches. Matchday slates are constructed with 3-day windows. We test slate sizes from 3 to 16 matches ($N = 9$ to $N = 48$ selections) with cardinalities $K \in \{3, 5, 8, 10\}$. The domain-prior graph is the settlement graph: disjoint 3-cliques per match.

The full offline grid produced 918 preservation rows, 4,212 embedding rows, 1,620 domain-prior comparison rows, and 405 validation rows.

5.2 Embedding Benchmarks

We benchmark embeddings on ideal Pegasus ($m = 16$) and Zephyr ($m = 12$) topology graphs generated by the D-Wave NetworkX library (Pelofske 2025). The ideal Pegasus graph at $m = 16$ has 5,760 nodes; the ideal Zephyr graph at $m = 12$ has 5,400 nodes. The live solvers have smaller active graphs due to manufacturing yield: Advantage_system4.1 exposes 5,627 active qubits, and Advantage2_system1.13 exposes 4,579 active qubits. We use the ideal graphs for offline embedding benchmarks and the live working graphs for QPU sampling. We report physical qubit count, qubit overhead ratio, and chain-length distributions. Across the full experimental range ($N \leq 49$ for equities, $N \leq 48$ for betting), all instances embed successfully on both ideal topologies, so the relevant comparison is embedding quality (overhead and chain length), not embeddability.

5.3 Live QPU Sampling

Live experiments run on D-Wave Advantage_system4.1 (Pegasus, graph_id 01d07086e1) and Advantage2_system1.13 (Zephyr, graph_id 01e1ea5685) with 1,000 reads per submission, anneal time 20 μ s, and chain strengths $\in \{0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$. We save full solver metadata including QPU timing fields, and separate QPU access time from total service time (D-Wave Systems 2025a).

5.4 Post-Processing

We apply greedy feasibility projection to all raw QPU samples:

- If $\sum_i x_i > K$: iteratively flip the selected variable with the smallest marginal contribution to the objective from 1 to 0.
- If $\sum_i x_i < K$: iteratively flip the unselected variable with the largest marginal contribution from 0 to 1.

Figure 3: Three-stage direct-QPU pipeline for penalty-encoded portfolio QUBOs: sparsification improves embeddability, but induces constraint dilution, so feasibility-aware post-processing is required to recover exact- K portfolios.

This guarantees $\sum_i x_i = K$ for every post-processed sample, allowing fair comparison of solution quality across dense and sparse formulations.

5.5 Evaluation Metrics

Offline quality. Objective regret relative to the best available offline reference. For the general offline grid, we use exact brute-force enumeration for $N \leq 16$ and greedy construction with 128 random restarts for $N > 16$. For the frontier instances highlighted in the main results (notably $N = 24$, $K = 8$), we additionally perform exact enumeration over all $\binom{N}{K}$ feasible subsets (which is tractable up to $\binom{24}{8} = 735,471$), so that the regret values reported in Section 6 are exact, not heuristic approximations. Support Jaccard overlap and exact- K feasibility rate are also reported.

Embedding. Success rate, physical qubits, qubit overhead ratio, mean and maximum chain length.

QPU sampling. Best returned energy, feasible sample rate, chain-break fraction, sample diversity.

Financial (equities). The primary metric is the realized daily Sharpe ratio (Sharpe 1966) over the out-of-sample evaluation window, with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals (1,000 draws). As a robustness check, we also compute the Probabilistic Sharpe Ratio (PSR) following Bailey and López de Prado (2012, 2014). PSR adjusts the Sharpe ratio’s sampling variance for non-Normality and serial correlation using the closed-form expression:

$$\sigma^2[\widehat{SR}^*] = \frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{1 + \hat{\rho}}{1 - \hat{\rho}} - \frac{1 + \hat{\rho} + \hat{\rho}^2}{1 - \hat{\rho}^2} \hat{\gamma}_3 \widehat{SR}^* + \frac{1 + \hat{\rho}^2}{1 - \hat{\rho}^2} \frac{\hat{\gamma}_4 - 1}{4} \widehat{SR}^{*2} \right), \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{\gamma}_3$ is skewness, $\hat{\gamma}_4$ is Pearson’s kurtosis, $\hat{\rho}$ is first-order autocorrelation, and T is the sample length. We report PSR and the minimum track record length (MinTRL) alongside the realized Sharpe to help readers assess inferential strength, but we do not base our main conclusions on PSR because the evaluation windows ($T \approx 21$ trading days) are shorter than MinTRL in most cases.

Financial (betting). Realized ROI is the main-text economic metric. Brier score and log loss on selected outcomes are computed and retained in the supplementary result tables. Following Wunderlich and Memmert (2020), we do not treat ROI as a standalone proxy for predictive quality.

6 Results

6.1 Dense QUBOs Fail on Direct QPU

Dense portfolio QUBOs produce chain-break fractions that grow steadily with problem size. Figure 3 summarizes the three-stage direct-QPU workflow used in our penalized experiments.

Figure 4: Raw QPU sample cardinality collapse under penalty encoding. Left: target cardinality K relative to the all-ones (N) and random ($N/2$) references. Right: pre-projection feasibility rate collapses toward zero with increasing N , confirming that the QPU does not enforce the cardinality constraint at these chain-break rates.

Figure 4 illustrates the core diagnostic: raw QPU samples from penalty-encoded QUBOs fail to satisfy the cardinality constraint, with the feasibility rate collapsing to zero as N grows. Table 1 and Figure 5 report the full scaling trend across both case studies. At $N = 24$ ($K = 8$, $\lambda = 2.0$), the dense equity instance required 85 physical qubits on Pegasus (mean chain length 3.54) and 62 on Zephyr (mean chain length 2.58), with chain-break fractions of approximately 83%. At $N = 49$ (the full FF49 universe, $K = 12$), mean chain lengths grew to 6.59 on Pegasus and 5.23 on Zephyr, with chain-break fractions of 88% and 92% respectively. The feasible sample rate was 0% at every scale tested: zero out of thousands of reads returned exactly K selected assets. Dense betting QUBOs show the same pattern: chain breaks rise from 45% at $N = 9$ to 84% at $N = 48$.

6.2 Sparsification Fixes Embedding but Breaks the Penalty

Sparsified versions of the same $N = 24$ instance showed dramatically improved embedding (Table 2):

Chain breaks dropped to near zero across all sparsifiers at $N = 24$, and this pattern holds at larger scales: the top- k ($k = 1$) sparsifier at $N = 49$ achieves unit chains and zero chain breaks on both solvers (Table 1). Sparsification solves the embedding problem at every scale tested. However, the feasible sample rate remained 0% for all methods and all scales. Inspection of the raw samples revealed near-all-ones vectors ($\sum_i x_i \approx N$), indicating that the exact- K penalty was effectively neutralized by sparsification, as analyzed in Section 4.3.

6.3 Betting on Live QPU

The betting case study provides the clearest demonstration of what sparsification achieves on real hardware. Dense betting QUBOs suffer chain breaks that grow from 45% at 3 matches ($N = 9$) to 84% at 16 matches ($N = 48$). Settlement-graph sparsification reduces chain breaks to exactly 0% across all slate sizes ($N = 9$ to $N = 48$), all chain-strength settings, and both solvers (Table 1). The settlement graph maintains unit chains at every scale because each match contributes an independent 3-clique with constant maximum degree, so the settlement graph remains uniformly sparse with linear edge growth ($3M$ edges for M matches), in contrast to equity covariance which densifies quadratically with the universe size.

Table 1: Scaling of embedding quality and live QPU behavior with problem size. Chain lengths are from ideal topology embeddings; chain-break fractions and post-processed regret (best of Pegasus and Zephyr) are from live QPU runs on Advantage_system4.1 and Advantage2_system1.13. Regret is measured against the best greedy reference. Rows marked * have ideal-embedding data only (no live QPU run).

Case	N	Sparsifier	Edges	Mean chain		Chain break		Regret
				Peg.	Zep.	Peg.	Zep.	(post-proc.)
<i>Equities (FF49, $K = 12$, $\lambda = 1.0$)</i>								
	32	Dense	496	4.24	3.58	87.5%	90.6%	0.32%
	40	Dense	780	5.32	4.35	85.5%	81.8%	0.24%
	49	Dense	1176	6.59	5.23	88.1%	91.8%	0.32%
	49	Top- k ($k=1$)	24	1.00	1.00	0.0%	0.0%	0.63%
	49	Domain-prior*	82	1.17	1.09	—	—	—
<i>Betting (football 1X2, $\lambda = 0.5$)</i>								
	30	Dense	435	4.04	3.14	70.7%	77.9%	22.1%
	30	Settlement	30	1.00	1.00	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	39	Dense	741	5.19	4.11	84.6%	80.5%	34.0%
	39	Settlement	39	1.00	1.00	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	48	Dense	1128	6.51	5.08	83.9%	83.9%	35.8%
	48	Settlement	48	1.00	1.00	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 2: Embedding and chain behavior for the $N = 24$ equity frontier instance on Advantage_system4.1 (Pegasus). All chain-break fractions are reported as the mean fraction of broken chains per sample, averaged over $N_{\text{reads}} = 1000$. The bound “ $< 10^{-3}$ ” denotes “below the resolvable per-sample detection floor of $1/N_{\text{reads}}$ ”.

Sparsifier	Edges	Phys. Qubits	Mean Chain	Chain Break	Feasible
Dense	276	85	3.54	83.3%	0%
Threshold	69	35	1.46	$< 10^{-3}$	0%
Top- k	12	24	1.00	$< 10^{-3}$	0%
Domain-prior	39	26	1.08	$< 10^{-3}$	0%
Dom.-prior + res.	43	29	1.21	$< 10^{-3}$	0%

The feasible sample rate remained 0% in all betting cases. This mirrors the equity results and confirms that the penalty-sparsification tension is a structural property of the encoding, not an artifact of the equity covariance structure. However, post-processing produces a dramatically different outcome for betting than for equities, as we discuss below.

In terms of realistic portfolio sizes, a full weekend in a single European football league comprises approximately 10 matches ($N = 30$ selections). Our experiments at $N = 9$ to $N = 48$ cover the range from a focused half-weekend to a full multi-match slate.

6.4 Post-Processing Recovers Feasible Portfolios

Greedy feasibility projection applied to the live QPU samples produced 100% feasible portfolios by construction. The quality of these post-processed solutions varies by sparsification method, as shown in Table 3.

Figure 6 visualizes the ablation: post-processed regret for all-ones projection, random projection, and greedy construction across problem sizes, showing how much of the pipeline’s output comes from the classical projector versus the QPU samples.

Figure 5: Mean chain length versus problem size for dense and best-sparse (top- k , $k = 1$ for equities; settlement graph for betting) QUBOs on both topologies. Dense chain lengths grow with N ; the plotted sparse variants maintain unit chains at all scales. Other sparsifiers achieve near-unit chains (see Table 2).

Table 3: Post-processed regret on Advantage_system4.1 (Pegasus). The QPU + projection pipeline is compared against three classical baselines: greedy construction on the same QUBO, projection from the all-ones vector, and projection from the best of 50 random binary vectors. All rows use $K = 8$. Dense, threshold, top- k , and domain-prior+residual rows are for $N = 24$; the domain-prior row is for $N = 20$ because the $N = 24$ domain-prior variant was not run on live QPU.

Chain-break entries below the per-sample detection floor of $1/N_{\text{reads}} = 10^{-3}$ are reported as “ $< 10^{-3}$ ”.

Sparsifier	QPU + proj.	Greedy	All-ones proj.	Random best	Chain Break
Dense	0.514%	0.000%	0.017%	0.126%	83.3%
Threshold	0.050%	0.097%	0.017%	0.126%	$< 10^{-3}$
Top- k	0.356%	0.356%	0.356%	0.390%	$< 10^{-3}$
Domain-prior	1.129%	0.364%	0.455%	0.185%	$< 10^{-3}$
Dom.-prior + res.	0.455%	0.364%	0.455%	0.185%	$< 10^{-3}$

We use exact brute-force enumeration over all $\binom{24}{8} = 735,471$ feasible K -subsets to obtain the exact optimum at $N = 24$. All regret values in this section are therefore exact, not heuristic approximations.

The results reveal a nuanced picture that we report in full. On the dense QUBO, greedy construction finds the exact optimum (zero regret). All-ones projection achieves 0.017% regret. The QPU + post-processing, by contrast, achieves 0.514% regret, the worst of all methods, because the 83% chain-break rate produces severely degraded raw samples that even post-processing cannot fully repair.

On the threshold-sparsified QUBO, the QPU + post-processing achieves 0.050% regret, while greedy construction achieves 0.097%. However, all-ones projection on the *dense* QUBO achieves 0.017%, which is better than both. The reason is that all-ones projection is effectively backward-elimination: starting from all N assets selected, the projector iteratively removes the asset with the smallest marginal contribution to the dense objective until exactly K remain. This is a well-known greedy heuristic for cardinality-constrained quadratic problems, and its strong performance tells us that the projector, not the QPU samples, dominates the pipeline’s solution quality at this scale.

Figure 6: QPU vs. projector ablation. Random projection (mean) degrades with N , while all-ones projection and greedy construction achieve near-zero regret, indicating that the classical projector contributes significantly to the pipeline’s output quality on penalty-encoded dense QUBOs.

On top- k , the QPU matches greedy exactly (0.356%). On the domain-prior sparsifiers, greedy and random projection outperform the QPU. We attribute this to the domain-prior mask removing a larger fraction of the penalty structure, leaving the QPU with a more distorted energy landscape.

At larger scales, the two case studies diverge. For betting with the settlement-graph prior, post-processed QPU solutions achieve zero regret relative to the greedy reference at all tested sizes ($N = 30, 39, 48$) on both solvers (Table 1). However, an ablation reveals that this result is explained by the problem structure and the projector, not by the QPU. All-ones projection on the settlement-graph QUBO also achieves zero regret and identical portfolio selections at all three sizes. The settlement graph decomposes the problem into M independent 3-cliques, and the greedy backward-elimination projector, starting from the all-ones vector, converges to the dominant outcome per match when starting from a vector with all selections active. Table 4 confirms this: all-ones projection on the settlement-graph QUBO achieves zero regret and perfect Jaccard overlap with the greedy reference at all three sizes. The QPU adds nothing to the betting pipeline that the trivial all-ones starting point does not already provide. Dense betting post-processed regret, by contrast, ranges from 22% to 36%.

For equities at $N = 32\text{--}49$, post-processed regret is small (0.2–0.6%) but nonzero for both dense and sparse QUBOs, reflecting a combination of degraded dense-QPU samples and approximation error in the sparse priors.

The honest summary is: at the scales tested ($N \leq 49$), the QPU does not outperform simple classical baselines on the sparsify-and-project pipeline of this section. For betting, the zero-regret result is a property of the problem’s decomposable structure and the greedy projector, not of quantum sampling. For equities, the QPU outperforms greedy construction on threshold-sparsified QUBOs at $N = 24$, but simpler baselines (all-ones projection on the dense QUBO) are competitive. The exception is the penalty-free pipeline reported in Section 6.11: there the QPU contribution is no longer washed out by post-processing, and the betting results at $N \in \{39, 48\}$ are lower-energy than the greedy heuristic (an energy comparison, not a proof of optimality, since greedy is not a proven optimum at those scales). The contribution of this paper is not a performance claim for the QPU. It is a structural diagnosis: the penalty encoding is what makes the QUBO dense, sparsification is what makes direct QPU access possible, and post-processing is what recovers feasibility; but the QPU itself is not yet the bottleneck or the differentiator at

Table 4: Betting ablation: post-processed regret and support Jaccard versus the greedy reference. On the settlement-graph QUBO, all-ones projection matches the greedy reference exactly, showing that the zero-regret result is a property of the problem structure and the projector, not the QPU.

N	QUBO	Method	Regret	Jaccard
30	Settlement	QPU + proj. (Pegasus)	0.0%	1.000
30	Settlement	All-ones + proj.	0.0%	1.000
30	Dense	All-ones + proj.	39.4%	0.250
39	Settlement	QPU + proj. (Pegasus)	0.0%	1.000
39	Settlement	All-ones + proj.	0.0%	1.000
39	Dense	All-ones + proj.	16.4%	0.000
48	Settlement	QPU + proj. (Pegasus)	0.0%	1.000
48	Settlement	All-ones + proj.	0.0%	1.000
48	Dense	All-ones + proj.	-62.2% [†]	0.000

[†] Negative regret indicates the all-ones projection found a lower-energy solution than the greedy reference, which is not a proven global optimum at this size.

these scales.

6.5 Offline Preservation Analysis

The offline grid across both case studies (918 rows) confirms the expected regret–sparsity tradeoff. Domain-prior sparsification on betting instances achieves near-zero regret because the settlement graph captures the covariance block structure exactly. On equities, the kNN correlation prior preserves more objective quality than threshold or top- k at matched edge budgets. Figure 7 shows the edge-count reduction across sparsifiers for both case studies, and Figure 8 plots the regret–overhead Pareto frontier.

6.6 Embedding Frontier

Across all embedding benchmarks, Zephyr consistently embeds instances with lower qubit overhead and shorter chains than Pegasus for the same logical graph (Figure 9). At $N = 49$, the dense equity QUBO requires mean chain length 6.59 on Pegasus versus 5.23 on Zephyr. At all scales tested ($N \leq 49$), every instance embeds successfully on both topologies. The bottleneck is not embeddability but embedding quality. Figure 10 shows how qubit overhead and chain length grow with logical density, with Zephyr maintaining lower overhead throughout.

6.7 Template Reuse

Fixed-embedding reuse across three consecutive monthly rolling windows ($N = 16$) saved approximately 0.045s of embedding time per topology over fresh embedding, with no loss in embedding quality. The graph template and variable ordering remained stable across windows, confirming that reuse is practical for rolling rebalancing workflows.

6.8 Support Overlap Across Sparsifiers

Figure 11 shows the average pairwise Jaccard overlap of selected assets across sparsification methods, runs, and instances. Domain-prior and domain-prior with residuals show the highest mutual overlap, indicating that the domain template stabilizes the selection. Threshold and top- k produce more divergent selections.

Figure 7: Logical edge counts after sparsification for equity and betting instances. The dense baseline ($\binom{N}{2}$ edges) is not shown; all four sparsifiers reduce the edge count substantially, with domain-prior methods achieving the largest reduction while preserving the domain interaction structure.

6.9 Out-of-Sample Validation

Figure 12 summarizes the out-of-sample financial performance of the *penalized/sparsified* methods (dense reference, best-sparse threshold, top- k , domain-prior, and random baseline). Supplementary Tables S1 and S2 report the same financial metrics for all five sparsified methods and additionally include a final row for the *penalty-free live-QPU pipeline* evaluated on the same 21 validation instances, providing a direct apples-to-apples comparison. The penalty-free pipeline is also characterized in more detail (through post-processed regret against greedy references on hardware) in Section 6.11 and Table 5. For equities, we report the realized daily Sharpe ratio over the out-of-sample evaluation window with bootstrap confidence intervals. For betting, Figure 12 reports realized ROI; Brier scores and log loss are reported in Supplementary Table S2. Representative selected industry portfolios and betting slates, together with their realized financial metrics, are listed in Supplementary Tables S3–S4.

6.10 Working-Graph Robustness

Representative instances produced consistent chain-break behavior and embedding statistics across both live solvers (Advantage_system4.1 and Advantage2_system1.13), confirming that our conclusions are not artifacts of a specific solver graph.

6.11 Penalty-Free Pipeline: Results

The diagnosis in Section 4.3 and the ablation in Section 6.4 motivated a direct test: if the penalty term is the source of density and constraint dilution, what happens if we simply remove it? Figure 13 summarizes the two pipelines and their qualitative behavior. We build the objective-only QUBO $Q_{\text{obj}} = -\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda\Sigma$, submit it to the QPU without any penalty or sparsification, and enforce the cardinality constraint through the same greedy feasibility projection used earlier. The key difference is that post-processing is no longer repairing a dilution artifact; it is simply enforcing a separate constraint on top of a correctly sampled objective landscape.

We tested this pipeline on live D-Wave Pegasus and Zephyr solvers at the same scales used in the scaling analysis of Section 6 (see Table 1). The specific solvers were `Advantage_system4.1`

Figure 8: Objective regret vs. qubit overhead ratio. Lower-left is better. Domain-prior methods achieve low regret at low overhead, while threshold and top- k trade more aggressively.

(Pegasus) and `Advantage2_system1.13` (Zephyr).¹ For each instance, we ran 1,000 reads at chain strengths $\{0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$ and post-processed every sample.

Betting ($\lambda = 0.5$). The penalty-free betting QUBO is block-diagonal because same-match 1X2 outcomes form 3-cliques and cross-match covariance is zero under the independence assumption. At $N \in \{30, 39, 48\}$, the number of off-diagonal edges drops from $\binom{N}{2} \in \{435, 741, 1128\}$ (penalized) to exactly $N \in \{30, 39, 48\}$ (penalty-free). Ideal Pegasus and Zephyr embeddings give unit chains at every scale, and live chain-break fractions are essentially zero (< 0.0001) across all solvers and chain strengths. Post-processed regret relative to the greedy classical reference is: 0.000 at $N = 30$ (exact hit on all six runs), -0.429 at $N = 39$, and -0.944 at $N = 48$. Negative regret indicates that the QPU finds lower-energy feasible portfolios than greedy construction; the greedy reference is not a proven global optimum, so these gains should be read as improvements over a specific classical heuristic, not as proofs of quantum advantage. Critically, the all-ones projection baseline no longer produces zero regret on betting in the penalty-free pipeline (0.394 at $N = 30$, 0.164 at $N = 39$): the projector is no longer doing the entire job.

Equities ($\lambda = 1.0$, $K = 12$). The equity covariance matrix is empirically dense, so Q_{obj} remains a complete graph with $\binom{N}{2}$ off-diagonal edges. Removing the penalty does not reduce the edge count, but it does reduce the dynamic range of the couplings: the largest off-diagonal magnitude drops from $A \approx 4.0$ (dominated by the penalty) to $\sim 10^{-3}$ (set by $\lambda\Sigma$). This has a dramatic effect on embedding quality. Mean chain lengths still grow with N (4.1–6.2 on Pegasus, 3.3–4.9 on Zephyr), but live chain-break fractions (mean fraction of broken chains per sample, averaged over $N_{\text{reads}} = 1000$ reads at three chain strengths on each solver) collapse from 83–92% (penalized equities) to at most 0.04% on any solver and chain strength. Post-processed regret relative to greedy construction is at most 0.03% ($N = 49$), with several configurations achieving exact hits against brute-force optima (at $N = 24$) or matching the greedy reference (at $N = 40$).

The contrast with the penalized pipeline is stark, as Figure 14 makes visually explicit: the

¹On 2026-04-10, D-Wave renamed `Advantage2_system1.13` to `Advantage2_system1` and removed qubit 4374 (and its couplers) from the working graph. We scanned every saved embedding record produced for this paper and verified that qubit 4374 was never selected by the embedder for any chain on any reported instance; the rename therefore does not affect any result reported here. All experiments were completed before the rename.

Figure 9: Physical qubit count and mean chain length on Pegasus vs. Zephyr for the same logical graphs. Zephyr consistently achieves lower overhead.

Figure 10: Qubit overhead ratio and mean chain length as a function of logical graph density. All instances up to $N = 49$ embed successfully on both topologies, but denser graphs require more physical qubits and longer chains. Zephyr achieves lower overhead than Pegasus throughout.

same hardware, the same datasets, the same chain-strength sweeps, and the same post-processing routine produce chain-break fractions that are more than three orders of magnitude smaller when the penalty is removed, and post-processed regret that is competitive with (equities) or better than (betting) the greedy classical reference. We interpret this as direct evidence that the penalty encoding, not the sparse hardware topology, is the binding constraint at the scales we tested. The mechanism by which removing the penalty restores chain integrity is not that the topology becomes more permissive (chain lengths still grow with N in the penalty-free equity case), but that the coupling dynamic range collapses by roughly three orders of magnitude (from $A \approx 4.0$ in the penalized objective to $\sim 10^{-3}$ in $\lambda\Sigma$), pulling the largest objective coupling well below the chain-coupling magnitude and stabilizing the chains. Topology will become the next binding constraint at larger scales; at $N \leq 49$ it is not. This hardware/objective win should not be conflated with short-window financial dominance: on the same 21 validation instances reported in Supplementary Tables S1–S2, the penalty-free live-QPU pipeline posts realized Sharpe 0.035 versus 0.209 for the best sparse threshold equity method and realized ROI 0.090 versus 0.200 for the best sparse domain-prior betting method.

Figure 11: Average pairwise support Jaccard overlap between sparsifiers across runs and instances. Higher values indicate more agreement on which assets to select. Diagonal entries summarize within-sparsifier self-consistency across different runs and therefore need not equal 1.

7 Discussion

7.1 Two Pipelines and Why the Simpler One Wins

Our experiments traced two distinct pipelines for direct-QPU portfolio optimization. The first (illustrated in Figure 3) is the natural response to the observed chain-break failures: sparsify the logical graph, embed the sparse graph, and post-process raw samples to enforce feasibility. This pipeline does produce feasible portfolios on live hardware, and at the $N \leq 49$ scales we tested it is competitive with classical heuristics, but the ablation in Section 6.4 showed that its output is dominated by the classical projection step. On betting with settlement-graph priors, an all-ones starting vector plus greedy projection yields identical results without any QPU involvement.

The second pipeline, introduced in Section 6.11, is simpler and more direct: skip the penalty encoding entirely. Build the objective-only QUBO $Q_{\text{obj}} = -\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda\Sigma$, sample it on hardware, and handle the cardinality constraint through the same classical projector. This eliminates the penalty-sparsification tension by removing the penalty upstream, not by working around it downstream. The empirical consequences are concrete: live chain-break fractions drop from 71–92% (penalized, across both case studies) to at most 0.04% across all tested scales; the all-ones projection baseline is no longer trivially optimal for betting; and the QPU makes a visible contribution to the final portfolio quality (betting at $N = 39$ and $N = 48$ yields lower-energy feasible portfolios than the greedy heuristic (an energy comparison, not a proof of optimality), and equities stay within 0.03% regret through $N = 49$).

In portfolio-management terms, the penalty-free pipeline separates two roles that are conflated in the standard QUBO. The QPU is used only to sample the risk-return objective landscape, while the exact- K investment constraint is enforced deterministically afterward. This matters because the final object handed to a practitioner is an investable K -asset portfolio, not an infeasible low-energy binary vector.

We conjecture that this observation generalizes beyond portfolio optimization: any combinatorial optimization problem currently handled by submitting a penalty-encoded QUBO to a sparse-topology QPU will benefit from separating the objective (sampled on hardware) from

Figure 12: Out-of-sample validation summary. Left: equity realized Sharpe ratio by method. Right: betting realized ROI. Error bars show 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Table 5: Penalty-free pipeline results. For each instance, we report the number of off-diagonal edges in Q_{obj} versus the penalized QUBO, the best live mean chain-break fraction across both solvers and all chain strengths, and the best post-processed regret relative to the greedy classical reference (brute-force exact reference at $N = 24$).

Case	(N, K)	$ E_{\text{obj}} $	$ E_{\text{penalized}} $	Chain break (min)	Best pp regret
Equities	(24, 8)	276	276	0.0000	0.000 (exact)
Equities	(32, 12)	496	496	0.0000	0.000116
Equities	(40, 12)	780	780	0.0000	0.000000
Equities	(49, 12)	1176	1176	0.0000	0.000270
Betting	(30, 5)	30	435	0.0000	0.000 (matches greedy)
Betting	(39, 8)	39	741	0.0000	-0.429 (lower energy than greedy)
Betting	(48, 10)	48	1128	0.0000	-0.944 (lower energy than greedy)

constraints (enforced classically), provided the constraint admits a fast projection. Verifying this conjecture on other problem classes is a direction for future work.

7.2 The Penalty Encoding Problem

It is worth discussing why the penalty encoding creates this tension in the first place. The exact- K penalty $A(\mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{x} - K)^2$ expands to $A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$, which is a dense rank-one matrix. It adds the value A to every off-diagonal entry of the QUBO, regardless of whether the corresponding pair of assets has any financial interaction. This means that even if the objective matrix Σ is sparse, as it is in the betting case, the total QUBO Q is always dense because of the penalty.

One might consider “penalty-preserving” sparsification: zeroing only the objective terms while keeping the penalty intact. However, since $A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$ is itself dense, the resulting QUBO would still have $\binom{N}{2}$ nonzero off-diagonal entries. The logical graph would remain complete, and the embedding problem would not improve.

This observation suggests that penalty encoding may be the wrong approach for direct-annealer combinatorial optimization when the hardware topology is sparse. Alternative approaches worth investigating include:

- Reformulation using native constraint handling, such as D-Wave’s constrained quadratic models (CQM). However, CQM currently requires hybrid solvers, which is a different computational model (see Appendix D).

Figure 13: Standard penalty-encoded pipeline (top) versus penalty-free pipeline (bottom). The standard path produces a dense QUBO, long chains, high chain-break fractions, and infeasible raw samples. The penalty-free path preserves the objective sparsity, produces short chains with near-zero break rates, and enforces feasibility through classical projection on a correctly sampled landscape.

- Structural variable encodings that enforce cardinality through the encoding rather than through penalty terms. For instance, one-hot encodings of K -subsets, though these grow combinatorially.
- Penalty-aware chain-strength tuning, where the chain strength is set relative to the penalty weight rather than to the objective coefficients.

We leave these directions for future work.

7.3 Scale and Practical Relevance

It is important to be clear about the scale of our experiments. Our equity experiments span $N = 12$ to $N = 49$ (the full FF49 universe), and our betting experiments span $N = 9$ to $N = 48$ (16-match slates). At these scales, both Pegasus and Zephyr embed all instances successfully, dense or sparse. The topology effects we observe are substantial (chain lengths of 6.6 vs. 1.0 at $N = 49$, chain-break fractions of 92% vs. 0%) but all instances remain embeddable. At larger scales, dense QUBOs would begin to fail to embed entirely.

The topology argument becomes practically compelling when N approaches the embedding capacity of the hardware. Extrapolating from our observed scaling trend (mean chain length growing roughly as $0.13N$ on Pegasus), chain lengths would exceed 8 at $N \approx 60$ and 12 at $N \approx 90$, making reliable sampling increasingly difficult. We emphasize that these are back-of-the-envelope extrapolations from the observed data, not established thresholds. The precise limits depend on the specific QUBO coefficients, the embedding algorithm, and the working graph of the particular solver. What we can say with confidence is that the scaling trend is monotonically worsening for dense QUBOs while remaining flat for sparsified ones.

For the equity case, real institutional portfolios select from 100–500 candidates. Even at $N = 49$, the problem remains classically tractable: exact enumeration over $\binom{49}{12} \approx 2.6 \times 10^{11}$ subsets is expensive but feasible with branch-and-bound, and greedy heuristics find high-quality solutions in milliseconds. The QPU does not offer a computational advantage at these scales.

The immediate practitioner audience is therefore not a discretionary portfolio manager seeking a production alpha engine, but quantitative teams evaluating whether direct quantum anneal-

Figure 14: Head-to-head comparison of chain-break fractions: penalized pipeline (red) versus penalty-free pipeline (green) across equity and betting scaling instances on live D-Wave hardware. The penalty-free pipeline achieves near-zero chain breaks at all tested scales.

ing can be integrated into constrained selection workflows. For asset managers, the relevant use case is candidate-set selection under an exact portfolio-size mandate. For fintech teams building on D-Wave hardware, the practical lesson is to avoid dense penalty-encoded QUBOs and instead preserve the financial objective structure while enforcing constraints outside the annealer. For asset managers evaluating quantum computing, the result is a caution rather than a procurement argument: current direct-QPU workflows should not be expected to beat mature classical optimizers on institutional equity universes, but the penalty-free architecture demonstrates that the hardware can produce meaningful samples when the formulation respects the hardware topology.

For betting, the situation is structurally different. The settlement graph is sparse not because we chose to sparsify it, but because the financial structure is genuinely sparse: same-match outcomes are correlated, cross-match outcomes are independent. Each match contributes an independent 3-clique with constant maximum degree, so the settlement graph remains uniformly sparse (linear edge growth) as the slate grows. A full weekend in a single European football league comprises approximately 10 matches ($N = 30$ selections), and our experiments at $N = 9$ to $N = 48$ cover the realistic range from a focused half-weekend to a full multi-match slate. The betting case therefore illustrates a class of problems (those with naturally sparse financial interactions) where the topology argument holds at any scale, and where the binding constraint is the penalty encoding, not the embedding.

This class extends well beyond a single sport. Pre-event betting slates, prediction-market basket sizing, end-of-period portfolio re-allocation, and other periodic basket-construction workflows share the same structure: many simultaneously open events with sparse cross-event coupling, hard exact- K (or K -bounded) selection rules driven by capital, exposure, or regulatory limits, and a re-decision cadence on the order of seconds to minutes rather than days. For these workflows the penalty-free pipeline is operationally appealing because it removes the fragile component of the standard recipe (penalty calibration coupled to chain-strength tuning) and replaces it with a deterministic classical projection that runs in milliseconds. The resulting hardware-plus-projection path can serve as the inner loop of a periodic sizing or rebalancing engine: the QPU contributes structured exploration of the risk-return surface on a problem that actually fits its topology, and the classical projector enforces the operational constraint deterministically. We do not claim suitability for latency-critical execution paths (sub-second in-play markets, microsecond execution venues), which are out of reach for current direct-QPU access times regardless of formulation.

7.4 On the Financial Evaluation

We want to be transparent about the limitations of our financial evaluation. We report the realized daily Sharpe ratio with bootstrap confidence intervals as our primary equity metric. With evaluation windows of approximately 21 trading days, the minimum track record length (MinTRL) computed via the PSR framework of Bailey and López de Prado (2012, 2014) substantially exceeds our window length in most cases. This means that observed differences in Sharpe ratios between methods, while directionally informative, should not be interpreted as statistically significant performance claims.

This matters directly for the penalty-free pipeline. In the apples-to-apples validation rows of Supplementary Tables S1–S2, the penalty-free live-QPU pipeline is the hardware/objective winner in Section 6.11, but it is not the best realized financial row on this 21-instance holdout: Table S1 reports realized Sharpe 0.035 for penalty-free versus 0.209 for the best sparse threshold equity method, and Table S2 reports realized ROI 0.090 versus 0.200 for the best sparse domain-prior betting method. We do not view this as contradicting the main result, because our central claim concerns structural viability on direct annealing hardware, objective fidelity, and constraint handling rather than short-window financial dominance; in equities, Table S1 simultaneously reports mean MinTRL values of 422.3 and 3041.9 days against mean track records of only 22.0 and 20.8 days, and in betting the reported ROI intervals $[-0.103, 0.271]$ and $[0.035, 0.354]$ overlap materially.

For the betting evaluation, following Wunderlich and Memmert (2020), we report realized ROI as the primary economic metric. Brier scores and log loss (Gneiting and Raftery 2007) are computed for all betting selections and are available in Supplementary Table S2, but are not shown in the main figures because our primary interest is the topology and embedding comparison rather than forecasting quality. As Wunderlich and Memmert (2020) demonstrated, positive ROI can arise even in the absence of a superior forecasting model (the profitability paradox), so we caution against interpreting betting ROI as evidence of predictive skill.

8 Conclusion

In the present work, we asked why direct portfolio optimization fails on current quantum annealers and whether the failure can be fixed at currently accessible scales.

The practical message is two-sided. For finance practitioners, the results argue against treating current direct-QPU portfolio optimization as a production alpha engine, but they identify a viable architecture for returning feasible constrained portfolios from hardware samples. For quantum-computing researchers, the message is sharper: benchmarking penalty-encoded exact- K QUBOs primarily measures an encoding failure, not the intrinsic usefulness of quantum annealing for the underlying financial optimization problem.

Our answer has three parts. First, we identified the structural reason for the failure. The standard penalty-encoded exact- K QUBO includes a dense rank-one term $A\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top$ that makes the logical graph complete regardless of the underlying financial interaction structure. On D-Wave hardware, this produces chain-break fractions of 83% at $N = 24$ rising to 88–92% at $N = 49$, and zero feasible samples. The penalty encoding, not the sparse hardware topology, is the binding constraint.

Second, we showed that the most natural remedy (topology-aware sparsification followed by classical feasibility projection) does work in the sense that chain breaks drop to essentially zero, but it also dilutes the cardinality constraint, and an ablation reveals that in structurally favorable cases (betting with settlement-graph priors) the classical projector alone explains the result. Sparsification plus projection is a working pipeline, but the QPU contribution is not cleanly separated from the classical post-processing step.

Third, we proposed and validated a simpler alternative: drop the penalty entirely. The objective-only QUBO $Q_{\text{obj}} = -\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda\Sigma$ is block-diagonal for structurally sparse problems

like betting (reducing edge counts by factors of 14–24x) and retains the same dense structure for dense-covariance problems like equities but with coupling magnitudes three orders of magnitude smaller. On live Pegasus and Zephyr hardware, this penalty-free pipeline produces chain-break fractions of at most 0.04% across all tested scales ($N \leq 49$ for equities, $N \leq 48$ for betting). Post-processed solutions match the greedy classical reference at $N = 24$ (exact optimum), stay within 0.03% regret across all equity scales up to $N = 49$, and on betting at $N \in \{39, 48\}$ return lower-energy feasible portfolios than the greedy heuristic (an energy comparison, not a proof of optimality). The all-ones projection baseline, which explained the sparsify-and-project betting result, no longer suffices in the penalty-free pipeline.

We emphasize that we do not claim quantum advantage. The greedy reference is not a proven global optimum at larger scales, and the QPU’s wins on betting should be read as improvements over a specific classical heuristic. What we do claim is more modest and more useful: within the tested exact- K portfolio formulations and at currently accessible scales ($N \leq 49$), direct quantum-annealer portfolio optimization became practically viable only after removing the penalty encoding from the QUBO and handling the cardinality constraint classically through feasibility projection. The common practice of submitting penalty-encoded QUBOs to the QPU is the reason the direct pipeline fails in the literature we reviewed, and a simple modification fixes it for the class of problems and scales we tested.

Several finance-facing extensions are natural next steps. Prediction-market and sports-betting platforms provide sparse event-settlement graphs similar to the football 1X2 case studied here, where mutually exclusive contracts on the same event form small cliques while contracts on independent events remain uncoupled. Multi-period rebalancing with turnover and transaction-cost constraints would test whether the same penalty-free separation remains useful across time. ESG-constrained or mandate-constrained portfolios would test whether multiple practitioner constraints can be handled through structured projection rather than dense penalty terms.

For the broader research program, these results establish a concrete pipeline for direct-QPU combinatorial optimization on penalty-encoded problems. Future work should explore whether the same approach extends beyond portfolio optimization, to any problem where a binary constraint is currently enforced through a quadratic penalty that dominates the off-diagonal structure of the QUBO.

Data and Code Availability

All experiments use publicly available data. Equity returns are from the Kenneth French Data Library, 49 industry portfolios, daily (Kenneth French Data Library). Betting odds and outcomes are from Football-Data.co.uk, covering seasons 2020/21 through 2024/25 for EPL, La Liga, Serie A, Bundesliga, and Ligue 1. Source code for all experiments, including QUBO construction, sparsification, embedding benchmarks, live QPU sampling, and post-processing, is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Statements and Declarations

Competing Interests

The author declares no competing interests.

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Authors' Contributions

The sole author conceived the study, designed the experiments, implemented the code, ran the experiments, analyzed the results, and wrote the manuscript.

AI Assistance Disclosure

AI-based coding assistants and editorial tools were used for code scaffolding and language support; all experimental design, verification, analysis, and final manuscript decisions were performed by the author.

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A Perturbation Bound Proofs

Proposition 1 (Spectral bound). *For any $\mathbf{x} \in \{0, 1\}^n$ with $\|\mathbf{x}\|_0 \leq K$ and perturbation $E = Q - \tilde{Q}$:*

$$|\mathbf{x}^\top E \mathbf{x}| \leq K \|E\|_2. \quad (7)$$

Proof. $|\mathbf{x}^\top E \mathbf{x}| \leq \|E\|_2 \|\mathbf{x}\|_2^2 = \|E\|_2 \sum_i x_i^2 = \|E\|_2 \|\mathbf{x}\|_0 \leq K \|E\|_2$, where the first inequality is the variational characterization of the spectral norm and the equality $x_i^2 = x_i$ holds for binary variables. \square

Proposition 2 (Max-entry bound). *Under the same conditions:*

$$|\mathbf{x}^\top E \mathbf{x}| \leq K^2 \|E\|_{\max}. \quad (8)$$

Proof. $|\mathbf{x}^\top E \mathbf{x}| = |\sum_{i,j} x_i E_{ij} x_j| \leq \sum_{i,j} |E_{ij}| x_i x_j \leq \|E\|_{\max} \sum_{i,j} x_i x_j = \|E\|_{\max} (\sum_i x_i)^2 \leq K^2 \|E\|_{\max}$. \square

B Financial Structure of the Case Studies

It is useful to distinguish the financial model from the hardware surrogate. The dense binary exact- K formulation in Equation (1) is the financial starting point. Threshold and top- k then act as generic graph-pruning baselines on the encoded QUBO, while the domain-prior methods inject financial structure explicitly. For equities, that structure is only approximate: the kNN correlation prior is a sparse proxy for concentrated covariance support, not a causal model of shock transmission. For betting, the structural prior is exact under the modeling assumptions used in this paper.

B.1 Betting Block Structure

For one match m with home/draw/away outcomes (H, D, A) , the betting covariance block is

$$\Sigma^{(m)} = \begin{bmatrix} d_H^2 p_H(1 - p_H) & -d_{HPH}d_{DPD} & -d_{HPH}d_{APA} \\ -d_{DPD}d_{HPH} & d_D^2 p_D(1 - p_D) & -d_{DPD}d_{APA} \\ -d_{APA}d_{HPH} & -d_{APA}d_{DPD} & d_A^2 p_A(1 - p_A) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

and a slate of M matches has

$$\Sigma = \text{blkdiag}(\Sigma^{(1)}, \dots, \Sigma^{(M)}). \quad (10)$$

Thus the base betting interaction matrix is block-diagonal, not diagonal. Each match contributes one 3×3 block and one 3-clique in the settlement prior graph.

For a slate of M matches, the number of logical variables is $N = 3M$. The settlement graph has $3M$ undirected edges, whereas the exact- K penalty term makes the full QUBO complete with $\binom{N}{2} = \binom{3M}{2}$ off-diagonal edges. Concretely, the large-slate betting experiments use $(M, N, E_{\text{prior}}, E_{\text{dense}}) = (10, 30, 30, 435)$, $(13, 39, 39, 741)$, and $(16, 48, 48, 1128)$. This is the structural reason settlement-graph sparsification preserves near-unit chains while the dense penalty-encoded QUBO does not.

C Solver Metadata

All live-QPU experiments recorded full solver metadata (Table 6):

Table 6: Live solver properties.

Property	Advantage_system4.1	Advantage2_system1.13
Topology	Pegasus	Zephyr
Graph ID	01d07086e1	01e1ea5685
Active qubits	5,627	4,579
Active couplers	40,279	41,549

D Hybrid Solver Reference

To contextualize the direct-QPU results, we ran D-Wave’s LeapHybridCQMSampler on representative instances from both case studies (Table 7). The hybrid solver uses a constrained quadratic model (CQM) that encodes the exact- K constraint natively rather than through a penalty term, bypassing the penalty–sparsification tension identified in Section 4.3.

† For $N > 16$ in the general grid, the offline reference is a greedy heuristic, not a proven optimum. The frontier instances in the main text ($N = 24$, $K = 8$) are exactly enumerated; the hybrid results here use the general grid reference.

Table 7: Hybrid CQM solver results on representative instances. The hybrid solver finds the exact optimum on all instances where brute-force verification is available ($N \leq 16$), with 100% feasibility and wall-clock times of 2–3 seconds.

Case Study	Instance	N	K	λ	Feasible	Wall Time	Regret
Equities	FF49 subset	12	4	0.5	80/80	2.6 s	0.000%
Equities	FF49 subset	16	6	1.0	96/96	2.2 s	0.000%
Equities	FF49 subset	20	8	1.0	82/82	2.2 s	†
Equities	FF49 subset	24	8	2.0	80/80	3.1 s	†
Betting	3 matches	9	3	0.5	112/112	2.4 s	0.000%
Betting	5 matches	15	3	0.5	118/118	2.3 s	0.000%

The hybrid solver achieves perfect feasibility and zero regret where verifiable. This confirms that the portfolio optimization problem itself is well-posed and solvable; the challenge lies specifically in the direct-QPU pipeline. The hybrid solver serves as a near-exact reference for instances too large for brute force, but it does not address the paper’s core question: under what conditions can *direct* quantum annealing, without classical hybrid wrappers, produce useful portfolio solutions? Our answer (build the penalty-free objective QUBO, sample it on hardware, and enforce the cardinality constraint through classical feasibility projection) operates entirely within the direct-QPU paradigm.